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Research On Impact of Brand on Buyers' Behavior in Benin

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ABSTRACT

Branding is one of the most important factors influencing client decisions in today's environment. Customers are more likely to buy items and services from companies that have effective branding. When customers have access to positively branded products, they have a higher level of brand loyalty. It's much more exciting to try to figure out how the mechanism of branding influences consumer behavior and buying decisions. One of the key goals of this study is to better understand the branding variables that influence consumer purchasing decisions. Brand image, price, brand awareness, advertisement, and brand loyalty all have a significant impact on the purchase of various products and items. The study will concentrate its efforts in Benin, collecting data from customers and evaluating the elements that consumers value when purchasing items such as clothing. The regression experimental results indicated; psychological and social factors have a significant positive effect on the buyer's buying behavior of a brand, as well as there is a positive and significant effect of a brand factor on a buyer's buying behavior of a brand. Lastly, that the country of origin does not influence the buyers buying behavior.

Keywords

Brand Marketing, Brand Management ,Consumer Behavior ,Perceived Brand Uniqueness, Consumers Perception of a country origin

Introduction

In today's commercial world, marketers must be vigilant on understanding consumer behavior. Branding continues to play an important part in improving commercial success and is a tool that has a good impact on changing people's purchasing habits. One way a corporation can increase demand for its products is through eye-catching branding initiatives such as colorful packaging. Virtual reality stores can be used to test the effectiveness of packaging on brand selection. Buyers can select from a variety of alternatives with differing colors on the packaging.

Various research have been conducted over the last few decades on the various aspects that influence consumers' branding judgments and the procedures they go through before selecting a specific brand. Given the broad nature of branding, multiple studies have discovered various characteristics that influence a consumer's perception of specific brands, such as apparel and wear brands, automotive brands, and so on. Different trademarks are related with the values that products provide to purchasers. Customers prioritize speed and agility while selecting the appropriate vehicle for their needs. Some clients opt for vehicles that are safer than their alternatives. Because of these realities, producers should be required to present evidence of the predicted utility of the finished items they offer to customers.

Consumers are the primary drivers of production, branding, and marketing strategies. The profitability of commercial organizations is determined by consumer behavior when purchasing various commodities and products. Customers that have a poor preference for a product are less effective for the company's financial capacity. When sales are generally low, revenue generation is low, and expenses are less likely to be met. Companies must improve their ability to identify appropriate consumer choices and create consumer-sensitive products. Consumer research is thus an important procedure in business for brand designers and marketers to ensure that their products and services keep or grow their market share.

This research will look into the impact of branded items on consumer behavior and how it affects Benin's domestic businesses. Domestic industries would have the opportunity to realign their branding strategy with market demands identified through branding activities. Firms that use the correct tactics to promote their brand identities in the market might achieve market prominence. The following are some of the frequent questions that the study of marketing ideas will attempt to answer for brand creators: What do customers buy, why do they buy, when do they buy, how often do they buy, and why do they buy some things over others. These are critical questions for increasing customer behavior throughout time. In so doing, the research will aid brand creators in grasping various consumer related concepts that define a business' performance, that is; consumer differentiation, consumer retention, consumer trends and consumer-driven innovations. As such, the study will assess how the relationship between brand and consumer behavior has impacted Benin's domestic industries and commodity market.

Materials and methods

Hypotheses development and conceptual framework

Brand Marketing

A long-term strategic plan to maintain a brand's recognition and reputation is referred to as brand marketing. Customers must be able to perceive the product's distinctive nature throughout time, which necessitates changes in the message about its appropriateness. When new messages are given that improve a product's image in the market, the product life cycle might be extended. The strategic plan's major goal is to build a loyal consumer base that will increase over time. To accomplish so, marketers must maintain consistency and continue to communicate the brand's identity and values in meaningful and engaging ways. Companies should be prepared to utilize a strategy that evolves over time in response to shifting market trends. Feminism and

youth demands are two issues that must be addressed. These realities enable adolescents to become effective in making purchasing decisions from suppliers based on the assumption that the product has a better worth. As a result, brand marketing is a broad term that refers to a company's approach to communication, sales, and products. This is accomplished by emphasizing the brand as a whole through product advertising. Brand marketing methods can fail, especially when a firm's brand reputation is damaged, forcing the company to either try to restore its image or create a whole new brand. As a result, a company's brand reputation must always be protected in order for the plan to succeed. When a corporation starts a strategy, it must examine a number of long-term objectives.

Brand Management

Simply said, brand management is the process of applying tactics to raise a product's or brands' perceived value over time. Product prices must rise as loyal customers are built through favorable brand association and great awareness. The characteristics added to a product, as well as the raw materials used in the finished product, should be well explained. For example, in the case of sugary beverages, a corporation might elect to produce zero sugar beverages alongside sugary beverages. These activities enable a business to broaden the range of products and services offered to clients on the market. More sales are predicted as a result of such agreements.

There are a lot of well-known businesses in the globe that have carved out a niche for themselves over time. Coca-Cola, McDonald's, Microsoft, IBM, Procter & Gamble, CNN, Disney, Nike, Ford, Lego, and Starbucks are just a few examples of global brands that have grown over time. These companies cater to a variety of markets and provide items that cater to the demands of clients at various times. A brand does not have to be associated with a specific product. A single brand could encompass a variety of products and/or services. Toyota, for example, produces a variety of automobiles under the Toyota brand. The same can be said for other autos such as Ford and BMW, among many others.

Consumer Behavior

According to Engel Miniard, consumer behavior describes how people react to product experiences, ideas, and services. Consumer behavior is such an important component of business that it has a huge impact on a country's economy. When customers exhibit a positive trend toward consumption, governments earn more money from the value added tax category. Markets that are mature tend to have greater consumption trends, which leads to long-term economic growth and employment. The study of how consumers choose, utilize, and dispose of items and services, as well as their emotions, mental, and behavioral responses, is known as consumer behavior. This is one of the most crucial concepts for a marketer to grasp because it enables him or her to comprehend what factors impact distinct consumers' purchasing decisions. Personal variables, social factors, brand considerations, psychological factors, and the country of origin of the brand are all elements that influence consumer behavior.

- **Personal Factors**

Individuals' interests and attitudes are influenced by factors such as age, gender, and culture, among other demographic factors. Slaba (2019) discovered that age has a substantial impact on a customer's attitude about brand prices and purchase behavior in a research on how personal characteristics influence customer buying behavior. Generations and events in one's life are determined by one's age. Customers are divided into three groups based on their ages and experiences: generation X, millennials, and baby boomers. These age groups have a wide range of experiences and expect to interact with things in a variety of ways.

The majority of young buyers made purchasing selections based on a product's luxury and fashion. Hart (2008) also collected data from a sample of 821 customers in the online market to better understand the relationship between customer behavior and age. The goal of this study was to see how age influences personalization of online content, willingness to provide personal information, privacy concerns, and the ability to collect implicit web usage information. Age influences customer intentions for future online purchases, online experiences to date, perceptions of different web personalization, and privacy concerns. The study found that personal factors have a strong influence on their intentions for future online purchases. Other research that came to similar conclusions was: (Alhellat et al., 2017; Constantinides, 2004; and Escobar et al., 2017). These studies have backed up the need for new businesses to accept internet-based customers in order to be more effective in decision-making and sales. Because they invest in the market's human capital and investment demands, companies who invest in future trends have the ability to sustain their clients. They make adjustments in response to market technology advancements.

Alhamd et al. (2019) investigated the impact of personal characteristics on a buyer's purchasing behavior using age, marital status, and gender. Personal characteristics have no substantial impact on a customer's behavior, according to the study's regression analysis. Customers were impacted by factors such as product price, quality, and other market pressures, according to their findings. Further research revealed no significant differences between female and male customers, as well as single, married, and separated people. Other research, such as Husnain et al. (2019) and Malik et al. (2019), found no significant link between personal variables and customer purchasing behavior (2013). The study was determined to add understanding on the influences of personal characteristics on the buyer's buying behaviors based on the aforementioned literature review. The following is the researcher hypothesis based on this literature review:

Ha0: There is no significant influence of personal factors on buyer's buying behavior

Ha1: There is a significant influence of personal factors on buyer's buying behavior

- **Psychological Factors**

Individuals' responses to marketing communications are referred to as psychological elements. This is mostly determined by their attitudes and perceptions. Customers of Apple merchandise in China were studied by Xin and Endong (2013) to see if there was a link between customer motivation and purchasing behavior. The research focused on youthful buyers who are enthusiastic about Apple products. Customers chose product features such as their ability to suit the needs of younger generations in terms of product speed. The study

concluded that the attractiveness of Apple items has served as a motivator for customers, using qualitative research technique. This has had a big impact on client purchasing behavior and the development of the Apple market in China. Customers' positive attitudes of a BMCC fan page and their buy intention are positively related, according to Iranmanesh and Najafabadi (2013). Using some buyer's buying process models, Ibrahim and Najjar (2008) discovered that there is a direct link between customers' motivation and their purchasing behavior. According to Collado et al. (2012), a buyer's buying behavior and decision to purchase a product is directly related to their attitude toward the brand. Similar to Ramya (2016), found that customer motivation has a significant contribution to buyers' attitudes.

According to the findings, psychological characteristics have no clear link to internet shopping behavior. More consistently, Abuodha (2020), Ittaqullah et al. (2020), and Martinez et al. (2015) showed that there is little evidence to support the idea that psychological aspects influence purchasers' purchasing decisions. The study's second research hypothesis might be stated as follows, based on the above literature review: *Hb0: Psychological factors have no significant influence on buyer's buying behavior*

Hb1: Psychological factors have a significant influence on buyer's buying behavior

- **Social factors**

In their study on the impact of social factors on purchasing behavior among online buyers, Ramya and Ali (2016) discovered that social factors had a significant impact on the buyer's purchasing behavior. The study's precise goals were to look into the relationship between social media, family, and friends, as well as their impact on beauty and cosmetic clients' purchasing decisions. Further research revealed that the purchase behavior of beauty and cosmetic customers is strongly influenced by peers, social media, and family members. Atulkar and Kesari (2018) investigated the effects of a family member's moderation on impulse purchase behavior among customers in the Chinese retailing business. The impulse buying tendency, according to research, is a critical behavioral approach to client decision-making that influences impulse purchases. Various previous studies, they claim, have not supplied a sufficient background of impulsive buying behavior. Despite the fact that family members have an impact on a customer's purchasing behavior, few studies have convincingly demonstrated the nature of impulse purchases. The study found that the impulse buying tendency among customers in the retailing industry was significantly influenced by family and relatives.

According to Prasath and Yoganathen (2018), there is a favorable correlation between social media and online client purchasing behavior. Sharma and Bhatt (2018) discovered, however, that highly educated customers are more concerned with price, quality, and brand, and are affected heavily by other experienced customers. According to Baker et al. (2019), social media has a major impact on customer behavior. These findings advise businesses to advertise their brands' photos on social media channels. Customers have the ability to obtain product information and make purchasing selections for products that are shown online.

Bai et al. (2015) discovered a favorable relationship between social characteristics and customers' intentions to buy a brand in a study to evaluate how social contact between people influenced buying behavior. The

majority of brand companies use social media to promote their products. The articles are sponsored in order to appear in front of the majority of social media pages. However, there is insufficient evidence in the study to establish a strong link between social characteristics and product purchase intent. Furthermore, Pandey and Parmar (2019) discovered that good comments about a brand from coworkers, family, and friends influence purchasers' purchasing decisions. However, no significant link was found between client purchasing behaviors and social characteristics in the study. The third hypothesis can be stated as follows, based on the above literature review:

Hc0: Social factors have no significant effect on customer's intentions to buy a brand

Hc1: Social factors has a significant effect on customer's intentions to buy a brand

Perceived brand Uniqueness

The creation of a brand involves creating elements that are unique in nature such as unique visual expression, brand personality and positioning that makes a product different from its potential competitors in the market place. There is a lot that crosses a consumer's mind when they are familiar with a brand. They start to have a feeling they have seen it before since they recognize the unique features on the brand. The goal is to create a brand that stands out and is unique to be able to hold a desired position in the market. One of the most common mistakes companies have done in the past is trying to please everyone. The best thing to do first is to define the target audience from the start before the development of the brand designs to ensure the message passed is relevant and specific. Once you are sure of the target audience then strategize on the most effective ways to reach or communicate the brand identity.

How you tell the brand story and communicate it to the consumers is crucial. This is because that's when you tell the consumers what you stand for and what message you are communicating to those you hope to be your potential customers. Creativity and innovation is critical at this stage. Creating a unique perception on the consumer's mind requires in depth analysis of their needs, wants and expectations as well as reaction to the brand on the store. Companies have tried to use VR stores to collect such data so as to maximize on designing brands that attract consumer's attention easily

Consumers perception of country of origin

The country of origin of a product has an impact on your purchasing decision as a consumer. Consider this: the \$95 dress shirt you're wearing today was manufactured by a Mega firm based in Hong Kong for a large-scale retailer in the United States. The customer conducts additional research and discovers that the shirt was manufactured in Singapore and that the fabric was sourced from Pakistan. On the other hand, it may have been made in any of the 25 countries where the Hong Kong-based Corporation has a presence. The clothing has most likely traveled farther than any of us have in international trade. Such a scenario demonstrates the interconnectedness of global supply networks, prompting the question of whether we should be concerned about a product's place of origin.

According to studies, the country of origin has a significant impact on how a consumer views a product, whether positively or negatively. When a product's parts are created in multiple nations and assembled in another, determining the place of origin can be challenging. According to studies, the nation of origin is a surrogate for product quality, performance, reliability, prestige, and a variety of other product qualities. Consumers have been proven to have a good or negative attitude toward products created in specific countries, according to research. This bias exists for both end-users and industrial customers, as well as for individual products and products in general. Both developing and developed countries have biases based on their country of origin. When compared to products created in developed countries, those from less developed countries are seen to be riskier and of lower quality.

Methods

Participants and procedure

The material gathered was all primary data. Primary data, as defined by Leduc (2008), is information acquired directly from the target population, in this case customers. The data acquired aided the researcher in determining how brands influence consumer behavior. This study has been targeted for 250 potential participants in the city of Benin. The targeted respondents are consumers in different categories in the city. However, only 200 respondents accomplished the survey. The number responded in the survey was a clear representation of 80% of the targeted respondents, the survey and assured them that the information they provided was collected specifically for this study and would remain confidential even after the study was completed.

Measurements

Furthermore, the respondents to the survey were not forced to reveal their identities. The researcher utilized quick and basic questions with simple language to eliminate cases of incorrect information and unanswered questions in the questionnaire.

The questionnaire also included closed-ended questions. These questions gave responders a way to stay inside a defined range of responses. When questions are closed, the chances of ambiguity are reduced. Because the respondents are led in nature, the researcher ensures that they spend as little time as possible answering the questions. This made it easier to respond to questions and allowed the researcher to collect measurable and quantitative data. Unlike in open-ended questionnaires, in close-ended questionnaires, customers were more likely to respond, and ease of understanding through options provided. The questionnaire consisted of two major parts, Part A and part B. the first part aimed at obtaining background information of the customers involved in the survey, while the latter aimed at obtaining relevant information about the research objectives. The close-ended questions' answers were measured using 5-points Likert frame; 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral, 4-agree, and 5-strongly agree. All social factors, personal factors, psychological factors, brand factors and the brand's country of origin are all ordinal variables measured under 5-point Likert frame

(1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral, 4-agree, and 5-strongly agree). The scale provides clarity that promotes decision making on the respondents' views on the subject matter under investigations.

Data analysis

The study used regression analysis to test for causality relationship between the variables. Since the study focused on investigating the factors affecting consumer behavior, and the effect of brands on consumer buying behavior in Benin, two regression models were used. The first model used the purchasing behavior of the customers as the dependent variable, while personal factors, psychological factors and social factors were used as independent variables. The influences of the independent variables were tested to show how they influence the buyers' behaviors when making purchase decisions at different times. Personal factors included individual's interests and opinions influenced by age, gender and culture among other demographic characteristics. Psychological factors referred to an individual's response to marketing messages. This mainly depends on their perceptions and attitudes, while social factors are associated with the groups of people that individuals interact with such as family members, friends, colleagues at work, school colleagues, social media and other factors such as income and education level. The model can be developed as;

Where; Y is the buying behavior of the buyers is the constant variables are coefficients of regression model for X1 to X3 respectively

X1, X2, and X3 represent overall perceptions of the respondents on Personal factors, psychological factors, and Social factors represents the error term.

Results

Inferential statistics

The inferential statistic will be used to investigate the association between different factors and the buyer's buying behavior for a brand. Correlation and regression analyses will be used to investigate the association between variables.

-Correlation analysis

Spearman's correlation analysis was used to obtain the strength and the direction of association between the buyer's behavior (dependent variable) and factors (independent variables). Bilboaca and Jantschi (2006) posit that a Spearman's correlation value greater than 0.5 indicates a strong correlation, while a correlation value less than 0.5 indicates a weak correlation. Besides, a positive Spearman's rho value indicates a positive correlation (an increase in strength of one variable leads to an increase of other variables), while a negative Spearman's rho value indicates a positive direction in the association between the variables.

Table 1: Spearman's rho correlation statistics

Personal factor			Buying behavior	age of a buyer	gender of a buyer	level of income	status
Spearman's rho	Buying behavior	Correlation Coefficient	1.00				
	Age of a buyer	Correlation Coefficient	.806	1.000			
	Gender of a buyer	Correlation Coefficient	.535	.553	1.000		
	Level of income	Correlation Coefficient	.654	.610	.725	1.000	
	Status	Correlation Coefficient	.274	.210	.241	.099	1.000
Psychological factors			Buying behavior	brand uniqueness	quality of the brand	the popularity of a brand	brand price
Spearman's rho	Buying behavior	Correlation Coefficient	1.000				
	Motivation	Correlation Coefficient	.000	1.000			
	Perception	Correlation Coefficient	.493	.406	1.000		
	Attitude	Correlation Coefficient	.474	.008	.428	1.000	
	Beliefs	Correlation Coefficient	.142	.335	.202	.176	1.000

Social factor			Buying behavior	colleagues at work	social media	family members, and friends	education level
Spearman's rho	Buying behavior	Correlation Coefficient	1.000				
	colleagues at work	Correlation Coefficient	.307	1.000			
	social media	Correlation Coefficient	.271	-.147	1.000		
	family members, and friends	Correlation Coefficient	.290	.361	.244	1.000	
	education level	Correlation Coefficient	.353	.522	.355	.524	1.000
Brand factor			Buying behavior	brand loyalty	brand engagement	brand awareness	Identity/Im of the brand
Spearman's rho	Buying behavior	Correlation Coefficient	1.000				
	brand loyalty	Correlation Coefficient	.286	1.000			
	brand engagement	Correlation Coefficient	.237	.593	1.000		
	brand awareness	Correlation Coefficient	.313	.694	.761	1.000	

	Identity/Image of the brand	Correlation Coefficient	.757	.339	.267	.283	1.0
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The Spearman's rho correlation showed that the age of a buyer, gender, and the level of income has a strong positive correlation, while marital status has a weak positive correlation with the buyer's buying behavior. Such correlation means that the buyers' decisions to make purchases are guided by the factors that are consistently strong and supportive of their purchase decisions. On psychological factors, all variables; buyer's perception of brand uniqueness, perception of the quality of a brand, popularity of a brand, and buyer's perceptions about the price of the brand have a weak positive correlation on the buyer's buying behavior. Likewise, social factors; colleagues at work, social media, family members, and friends, and buyer's education level has a weak positive correlation with buyer's buying behavior. There is a weak positive correlation between brand loyalty, brand engagement, brand awareness, and identity/image of the brand and the buyer's buying behavior.

Test for Collinearity

The collinearity test was used to test the existence of is a strong correlation between the independent variables, which may influence the quality of regression analysis. Variance inflation factor was used to test for collinearity. A critical VIF value of 3.0 was used, where all variables with a VIF value greater than 3.0 were considered to exhibit multi-collinearity and therefore, exempted during regression analysis. The results were as in the table below.

Table 2: Collinearity Statistics

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Overall personal factor	.879	1.137
	Overall psychological factors	.666	1.501
	Overall social factors	.835	1.197
	Overall brand factor	.562	1.779
	Consumers perception of a country of origin	.598	1.671

the table, the overall personal factor (1.137), overall psychological factors (1.501), overall social factors (1.197), overall brand factor (1.779), and consumer's perception of a country of origin (1.671) gave VIF values less than 3.0. Therefore, there is no multi-collinearity among independent variables. Thus, all independent variables were used in regression analysis.

Causality Relationship

A causality relationship can be defined as an influence association. That is if one factor is affected (independent variable), it affects the other variable (dependent variable). To test for causality relationship between independent variables; buyer's perception of brand uniqueness, perception of the quality of a brand, popularity of a brand, and buyer's perceptions about the price of the brand and the buyer's buying behavior, the study used multilinear regression model. T-test was used as the test statistic, and independent variables with a t-value greater than 1.96 or a p-value less than 0.05 were considered to have a significant association/ have a significant influence on the buyer's buying behavior.

The regression coefficient indicated that there is a positive association between independent and dependent variables, while the negative regression variable indicates there is a negative association between independent and dependent variables. The findings were as in the table below. The model given by the formula; $Y=a+bx+-$ was applied in the analysis process.

$$Y=a+bX+-$$

$Y=$ Consumer perceptions of country of origin +overall personal factors +overall social factors+ +overall brand factors+ overall psychological factors.

$$Y=0.16+0.19+0.18+0.19+0.079= 0.799$$

$$R=0.799$$

Overall brand factors had the most influence is the psychological factors followed by personal factors. The factor with the least effect is psychological factor. Values of regression squares that are above 50% shows positivity in the factors considered as independent factors on their influence on the dependent factor. For this case, squaring the regression gives a value of .639 that is a above .5. Showing positivity of the independent variables considered.

4.5.3.1. Factors affecting buyers' behavior

Table 9: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
Regression	.799	.639	.630	.50680

This table presents a summary statistics of the model. The predictor variables were: (Constant), Consumers perception of a country of origin, overall personal factor, overall social factors, Overall psychological factors, and Overall brand factor

From this table, the regression analysis gave an R-Square value of 0.639, which indicate that the independent variables have a 63.9% influence on the buyers buying behavior. The adjusted R Square value was 0.63.

Table 10: ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	88.152	5	17.630	68.642	.000
	Residual	49.828	19	.257		
	Total	137.980	19			

The ANOVA analysis was used to test for the significance of the regression model. The Statistic F value was used as a test statistic. The hypothesis to be test states that, there is no significant joint association between independent variables and dependent variables. In this case, if the F statistic gives a significance value less than 0.05, we reject this hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant joint association between independent variables and dependent variables, which indicate the models can be used to show the association between the variables.

The ANOVA statistics gave an F statistic of 68.642 attributed with a significance value of 0.000. This shows a joint association between buyer's buying behavior and consumer's perception of a country of origin, overall personal factor, overall social factors, overall psychological factors, and overall brand factor. This indicates that the regression model used can be used to show the association between these variables. However, since the Squared-R value was less than 0.75, which is considered sufficient, the model cannot be used to predict the future buying behavior of the brand, using these factors.

Table 11: Coefficients of regression model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.381	.321		10.525	.000
	overall personal factor	.151	.036	.191	4.154	.000
	Overall psychological factors	.191	.050	.200	3.790	.000
	overall social factors	-.575	.046	-.585	-12.388	.000
	Overall brand factor	.189	.065	.168	2.921	.004
	Consumers perception of a country of origin	-.103	.058	-.099	-1.774	.078

The regression analysis gave a positive beta value for overall personal factors (0.151) and a significance value of 0.000. The significance value is less than 0.05, thus, there is a positive and significant association between the personal factors and buyer's buying behavior of a brand. Overall psychological factors also gave a positive beta value of 0.191, and a significance value less than 0.05, this shows that psychological factors have a significant positive effect on the buyer's buying behavior of a brand. However, the regression results gave a negative beta value (-0.575) for the social factor variable and a significance value of 0.000. Social factors have a significant negative effect on the buyer's buying behavior of a brand. There is a positive and significant effect of a brand factor on a buyer's buying behavior of a brand. This is confirmed by a positive beta value (0.189) and a significance value (0.004) less than 0.05. Lastly, the regression analysis shows that the causality relationship between a consumer's perception of a country of origin and a buyer's buying behavior of a brand is negative and insignificant. This is because there the regression coefficient for consumer's perception of a

country of origin is negative (-0.103), and has a significance value greater than 0.05, at a 95% confidence interval.

Discussion

The primary goal of this study was to look at the impact of a brand on a buyer's purchasing decisions. Personal characteristics such as a buyer's age, gender, income level, and marital status were used to describe personal behavior in the study. The mean of these characteristics, which is the overall buying behavior, had a favorable and substantial effect on the buyers' buying behavior. In other words, the purchase of behavior will be heavily influenced by the individual's age, gender, financial level, and marital situation. Alhelalat et al. (2017) found that personal characteristics play a significant role in a customer's behavior, which is consistent with the findings of this study. Case in point, Females are much more consistent with that brand with excellent quality, unique, and favorable to their taste, according to their poll to investigate customer behavior on internet companies. However, depending on the context of the brand type, the buyer's age and marital status alter the buyer's behavior.

The customers' perceptions of the brand's distinctiveness, brand quality, brand popularity, and brand pricing were all psychological elements in this study. Customers' motivation has a substantial impact on buyer's sentiments, according to Ramya (2016). If a buyer believes a given brand is of poor quality or is more expensive than usual, they are unlikely to purchase it. The regression results revealed important social aspects that influence a brand's buyer behavior. The study's findings revealed that customers are heavily impacted by their coworkers, social media, family, and friends, as well as the buyer's educational level as a social component. Similarly, a study of the elements that influence purchasers' purchasing behavior revealed that social influences have a substantial effect. According to Bai et al. (2015), the majority of brand companies use social media to promote their products. This draws a large number of people in. Furthermore, shopper purchasing behavior is influenced by social media remarks about a certain brand. If a brand receives positive feedback from customers, it is more likely to attract new customers. A brand element has a positive and significant impact on a buyer's purchasing behavior. Brand factors were represented in the study via brand loyalty, engagement, awareness, and image/identity. Case in point, Buyers who demonstrate brand loyalty, according to Moisescu (2006), are attached to the brand and are inclined to make purchases frequently or always. According to the findings, brand loyalty has a favorable and considerable impact on a buyer's purchasing behavior.

Limitations and Recommendation

The usage of the overall customer perception may not have accurately shown the relationship between a specific item in that component and the brand's purchasing behavior. The validity and reliability of the study's final conclusions are lowered as a result of this erroneous link. There is a potential that the results will be

different if the sample differs from the original sample. As a result, the study cannot be used to get a specific conclusion on each element of relevance, but rather to reach a broad conclusion based on these aspects.

The study was totally quantitative, despite the fact that empirical analysis was utilized to corroborate the findings. Only using quantitative data may have resulted in insufficient information about the true issue, as opposed to using both qualitative and quantitative data.

Limitation of time and cost. A limited sample size suggests that the results and conclusions reached in this study may not reflect the real situation, and that they may differ if a bigger sample size was employed.

The study suggested that a follow-up study be conducted in which every item in every favor be included in order to establish their impact on customer behavior. Furthermore, the study suggested that a future study with a bigger sample size than 200 be conducted, as this would provide more information regarding client purchasing behavior based on the parameters studied. Furthermore, the study recommended that a future study collect both qualitative and quantitative data from the population of interest, as this will help the researcher gain more credible information about the real situation, resulting in more legitimate results and conclusions.

Conclusion

Considering the aforementioned findings, the study employed many research findings from various countries and time periods to support its findings and reach a legitimate conclusion that can be applied not only to the demographic of interest, but also to a variety of other situations based on customer behavior. Customers' behaviors are defined as a relationship between their actions and their personal opinions. Customers' interests and purchasing habits are linked, according to the findings of this study. Supporting the opinions of customers is a crucial aspect of the buyer decision-making process.

References

- Atulkar, S., & Kesari, B. (2018). Impulse buying: A consumer trait prospective in context of central India. *Global Business Review*, 19(2), 477-493.
- Bhakar, S. S., Bhakar, S., & Bhakar, S. (2013). Relationship between country of origin, brand image and customer purchase intentions. *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business*, 10(2), 25-47.
- Bilgin, Y. (2018). The effect of social media marketing activities on brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty. *Business & Management Studies: An International Journal*, 6(1), 128-148.
- Chinomona, R., & Maziriri, E. T. (2017). The influence of brand awareness, brand association and product quality on brand loyalty and repurchase intention: a case of male consumers for cosmetic brands in South Africa. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 12(1).
- Collado Agudo, J., Herrero Crespo, A., & Rodríguez del Bosque, I. (2012). Adherence to customer loyalty programmes and changes in buyer behavior. *The Service Industries Journal*, 32(8), 1323-1341.
- Escobar-Rodríguez, T., Grávalos-Gastaminza, M. A., & Pérez-Calañas, C. (2017). Facebook and the intention of purchasing tourism products: moderating effects of gender, age and marital status. *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 17(2), 129-144.

- Malik, M. E., Ghafoor, M. M., Iqbal, H. K., Ali, Q., Hunbal, H., Noman, M., & Ahmad, B. (2013). Impact of brand image and advertisement on consumer buying behavior. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23(1), 117-122.
- Prasath, P., & Yoganathen, A. (2018). Influence of social media marketing on consumer buying decision making process. *SLIS Student Research Journal*.
- Ramya, N., & Ali, S. M. (2016). Factors affecting consumer buying behavior. *International journal of applied research*, 2(10), 76-80.
- Rusmiati, N. N., Sugiati, I. G. A., Purnami, A. S., & Amerta, I. M. S. (2020). The effect of brand image and country of origin on consumer buying interest: case study on Yamaha NMAX motorcycle in Denpasar city. *International Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 7(3), 83-90.
- Sharma, B. K., & Bhatt, V. K. (2018). Impact of Social Media on Consumer Buying Behavior-A Descriptive Study on Tam Model. *i-Manager's Journal on Management*, 13(1), 34.
- Slabá, M. (2019). The impact of the age on the customers buying behavior and attitude to price. *Littera Scripta*, 146.
- Xin, X., & Endong, Z. (2013). The Motivation Buying Behavior Influence the Chinese People Purchase Apple's Merchandise: A Survey of Apple Store in China. *Journal of Medical Science and Clinical Research Volume*, 1, 209-221.

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